

Predicting intention to share news through social media: An empirical analysis in Indonesian youth context

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Abstract:

The development of digital technology encourages the growth of social media. Social media becomes a platform for sharing news, information, images, and many other things. News spreads faster and becomes viral. This phenomenon can be regarded as a "news-find-me" phenomenon. The aim of this research is to assess the relationship between information sharing, entertainment, and socialization as three main predictors of attitude towards news sharing. This research also assesses the relationship between attitude and intention to share news. The data was collected through a survey with the non-probability sampling technique. Specifically, a purposive sampling design involving 200 respondents was applied. The data then were analyzed by applying structural equation modeling. Results show that all research hypotheses were supported.

JEL Classifications: M39

Keywords: Information sharing, entertainment, socialization, attitude, intention

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1. Introduction

The number of people that connected in the Internet is increasing every year. In Indonesia, there were 132,7 million people connected to the Internet in 2016, while the number made only 88 million people in 2014 (Widiartanto, 2016). The increase in the number of people with the Internet access is in line with the increased number of users in social media. Technology and social media has shaped people culture becoming the culture of sharing information.

However, news and information are sometimes shared rapidly by people without really understanding the news. In particular, people often share information that looks interesting and phenomenal without checking whether the news is true or just a hoax. The significant volume of news in social media forms the reality when people do not have to search for news but news that finds people who can be called "news-find-me perception" (Zuniga et al., 2017). The phenomenon of sharing news through social media is important because news can shape people in seeing other people, objects, brands, and many other things even the world.

Many researches have been conducted to predict news sharing behavior. Most of them applied the deductive method. In other words, many research applied variables that derived from existing theory, for example, the theory of uses and gratifications (e.g. Sheth & Kim, 2017; Apaolaza et al. 2015; Hsu et al. 2015; Lee et al., 2011; Ma & Lee, 2011; Hanson & Haridakis, 2008). On the other hand, a few research in news sharing context applied inductive method (e.g. Wong, 2017; Din & Haron, 2012). An inductive approach

is where the researcher begins with as few preconceptions, developing a model based on the phenomenon. However, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, research combining inductive and deductive approaches is rarely performed.

This paper aims to fill the gap. In particular, this study uses variables developed through an inductive approach, i.e. through an open questionnaire asking major antecedent variables in the intention to share news on social media. This research also applied the deductive approach by confirming variables found in inductive approach with the social media literature review. It can be stated that this research model was developed through an inductive and deductive approach. Thus, the aim of this research is to predict intention to share news through social media by examining three predictor variables (i.e., information, entertainment, and socialization) of attitude toward news sharing, and examining the relationship between attitude and intention to share the news.

2. Literature review

2.1. Social media

Social media is defined as a medium to socialize with each other and conducted by online that allows people to interact with each other (Bolton et al., 2013). Specifically, people interact through the use of web-based and technologies that making communication becoming more interactive (Baruah, 2012; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). The uses of social media have change people behavior in communication especially in social interaction without limited by time and location. Many medium are used for that socialization with each other such as Social Network Sites (e.g., Facebook, MySpace), weblog or blog, micro-blogging (e.g., Twitter), forums or online message, content communities (e.g., YouTube, Flickr), virtual game worlds, and virtual social worlds (Chan-Olmsted et al., 2013; Baruah, 2012; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Thus, by using social media, people can actively engage in a communication process that not only as information receivers but also as content creators (Chan-Olmsted et al., 2013; Uitz, 2012). Five main characteristics of social media platforms are: participation, openness, conversation, community, and connectedness (Mayfield, 2008 cited by Chan-Olmsted et al., 2013).

The impact of social media to people' life can be perceived in both positive and negative ways. In positive sides, social media enable people to communicate with others without limited by space and time and social media is cost effective. Through communication, people may share information, ideas, and many other things. Media social is also useful communication tool not only for people, but also for companies, stores, organization, political parties, and others. The main negative side of social media related to news sharing is about misinformation. Specifically, people tend to easy share news without checking whether news or information that they share are truthful or just hoax.

2.2. News sharing and the theory of Uses and Gratification

Why people share news in social media? One theory that is mostly applied to assess variables in predicting people behavior in social media is the theory of uses and gratification. This theory states that people are actively seeking certain media and certain content to produce certain satisfaction. In other words, based on this theory, people are actively considered and evaluate different types of media to achieve their communication objectives. Based on this theory it is also stated that the reasons for using the media are to spend time, togetherness, fun, escape from unpleasant situations, enjoyment, social interaction, relaxation, information, studying certain content and more. Then, it can be stated that the theory of Uses and Gratifications refers to people that actively select and

use certain media to meet certain needs. People can make choices and controls. Furthermore, people are self-conscious, and able to understand and articulate their reason for using the media. They see the media as one way to satisfy their needs. For this research, an exploratory research was conducted to determine reasons for sharing news in social media. Three main reasons for sharing news in social media: information sharing, entertainment, and socialization.

2.2.1 Information sharing

Information sharing refers to sharing content that will bring awareness to an issue, object, event, people, and others (Wong & Burkell, 2017). Social media is one main media that many people apply to share information, whether general information is or personal / specific information. Many social network site users have shared information / news stories or images rather than discuss that news issue or event (Anderson & Caumont, 2014). One main reason why people share in the social media is because they think that it will be helpful to the recipients (Mendelsohn & McKenna, 2010). Moreover, a study conducted by Pew Research Center in 2016 shows that 6 out of 10 Americans adult get news from the social media. In other words, more people know about news from social media rather than conventional media such as television, radio, or newspapers (Curry, 2016).

2.2.2. Entertainment

“Because I find it interesting / entertaining” is the number one reason why people share news in social media (Mendelsohn & McKenna, 2010). Social media has several benefits. One of the main benefits of social media is entertainment. In particular, people can have good time with their social media. News, pictures, games, photos, and many other things shared on social media give feelings not only to the avenger but also the sender. Two most feelings from social media are fun and relax, though negative feelings can also be happened. Furthermore, many people use their social media as ways to pass their spare time, dull moments, and even escape from their loneliness feeling by sharing, liking, or commenting on things that are shared in social media (Apaolaza et al., 2015).

2.2.3. Socialization

One of the main human needs is socializing with others. Social media through the medium of internet has revolutionized the way of socialization. People can interact with others without being restricted by distance and time. Through the medium also the users can find the existence of old friends, find new friends, and find people who have the same hobbies and activities. Though it is undeniable that socialization through social media sometimes is a virtual connection or "superficial" rather than real life relationship (Amedie, 2015).

2.3. Attitude toward sharing news

Attitude is defined a learned predisposition toward objects or behavior in a consistent way (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2015). Specifically, attitude is formed through direct experiences and learning. Attitudes affect the consumer's learning process that ultimately affects consumers in making decisions. In particular, attitudes play an important role in shaping

consumer preferences in deciding which brands to buy which consumers usually choose the most favored brands.

Attitude is also known as the explanatory concept that can help researchers and practitioners understand behavior, be they behavioral or behavioral changes consistent. Understanding of changes and consumer behavior contributes to marketing research. Furthermore, studies in the field of consumer behavior and marketing show that attitude is one of the main factors that can influence consumer choice. If the consumer has a positive attitude towards a brand, then the consumer has a great tendency to buy the brand. Conversely, if the consumer has a negative attitude towards a brand, it is very likely that consumers will not buy the brand. Consumer attitudes tend to be stable, or not easy to change. Furthermore, attitude is divided into three components: cognitive (i.e., beliefs), affective (i.e., emotions and feelings), and conative (i.e., intention to behave) (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2015).

2.4. Intention to share news

As one component of attitude, intention is one main antecedent variable in explaining behavior. Intention is defined as tendency to perform or to behave. Main attitude theories such as the theory of planned behavior and the theory of trying show intention as an intervening variable that exist in the relationship between attitude and behavior. In other words, it can be stated that people beliefs toward something (i.e., attitude) will then translated into tendency to perform behavior (i.e., intention) and finally perform the behavior. The hierarchy can be stated as attitude → intention → behavior. In relating with intention, several research applied intention as a proxy of behavior (e.g., Park & Blenkinsopp, 2009; Turchik & Gidycz, 2012). Furthermore, in marketing research, intention to buy is one important variable that will reflect consumer decision making (Bagozi, 2009).

2.5. Research model and hypotheses

FIGURE 1. RESEARCH MODEL

H₁: Information sharing is positively related to attitude toward sharing news

H₂: Entertainment is positively related to attitude toward sharing news

H₃: Information is positively related to attitude toward sharing news

H₄: Attitude toward sharing news is positively related to intention to share news

3. Research method

3.1 Sampling design and sample size

This study applied a non-probability sampling. Specifically, a judgmental sampling was used with two main criteria: respondent should ever share news in social media in the last 24 hours, and respondent should undergraduate students. Research sample involved 200 respondents. The sample size was an adequate size for analyzing data through structural equation modeling (Boomsma, 1985; Hox & Bechger, 1988; Kline, 1998). The sample size in this research was mainly based on practicality and research budget.

3.2 Measures

All measures were adapted from previous studies. Adapting measures from existing literatures ensure content validity. Specifically, entertainment was measured by applying 4 indicators that were adapted from Hsu et al. (2015). Similarly, information was assessed by using 4 indicators that were based on Hsu et al. (2015). Socialization was measured by 4 indicators which were adapted from Hsu et al. (2015) and Apaolaza et al. (2015). Furthermore, attitude and intention to share were measured which based on Ajzen (2006). Specifically, attitude was assessed through 4 indicators and intention to share was measured by 3 indicators. All indicators were anchored on a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 that means strongly disagree to 5 that means strongly agree.

3.3 Pilot test

The main purpose of the pilot study is to make sure the questionnaire can be understood by the respondents. Because the questionnaire was adapted from previous research, the translation from the original to the language used in the research is one of the main steps in the process of adaptation of the questionnaire. Thus, the clarity of the questionnaire is assessed through a small sample reflecting the target population and some experts (Patten, 2017; Borsa et al., 2012; Zikmund et al., 2010).

3.4 The goodness of measure

Two major criteria were applied to evaluate the quality of measures: reliability and validity analysis. Reliability refers to the consistency of measures. Reliability is a necessary but not sufficient for validity analysis. Validity shows the accuracy of a measure which truthfully represents a concept (Zikmund et al., 2010). This research applied Cronbach Alpha to assess reliability. In establishing validity, construct validity was assessed through evaluating convergent and discriminant validity.

3.5 Data analysis

Structural equation modeling was applied to analyze data. though SEM is usually applied as a confirmatory techniques, but it can be used for exploratory purposes (Schreiber et al., 2006). Furthermore, indices in SEM that are suggested for one time analyses are the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), and CMIN/DF because these indices are the most insensitive to sample size, model misspecification, and parameter estimates (Asiwe et al., 2017; Hooper et al., 2008; Schreiber et al., 2006).

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Response rate

Of the 200 questionnaires was distributed to the respondents, 196 were returned but 4 questionnaires can not be used since incomplete questionnaires, giving 192 usable response rates (96 %). All respondents were Business School students from batch 2017 and 2016. Most of the respondents are males (59%) as compared to females (41%).

4.2 Statistic descriptive

The means, standard deviations, and correlations for information, entertainment, socialization, attitude toward sharing news and intention to share news is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. MEANS, STANDARD DEVIATIONS AND MATRIX CORRELATIONS

Variable	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5
Information	3.657	0.667	1				
Entertainment	3.933	0.704	0.259**	1			
Socialization	4.100	0.662	0.253**	0.465**	1		
Attitude towards sharing news	3.666	0.615	0.384**	0.385**	0.417**	1	
Intention to share news	3.572	0.701	0.256**	0.299**	0.330**	0.506**	1

Note: ** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.3 Reliability and validity

The first stage of the analysis is to assess the reliability and validity of the measures. The reliabilities (Cronbach's alpha) ranged from 0.801 to 0.862, satisfying the criteria of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2007). This study also measures convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity was achieved as by applying an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and a confirmative factor analysis (CFA) (Wixom & Watson, 2001). Table 2 shows the evidence of all indicators were loaded in their respective component (i.e., variable). The Table also shows that one item (ATT1) was deleted due to cross loading. CFA analysis was also performed and the results indicated that all factor loadings were significant and varied from 0.599 to 0.862. Furthermore, the goodness-of-fit statistics were CMIN/DF = 1.795; CFI = 0.934; TLI = 0.919; and RMSEA = 0.065. These results showed that the convergent validity was achieved. Discriminant validity was assessed by observing the correlations between constructs (Table 1). The result shows that no correlations between

construct achieve higher value which could indicate that the indicators for a variable also measure another variable (Hair et al., 2007).

TABLE 2. EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

	1	2	3	4	5
INF1			0.826		
INF2			0.725		
INF3			0.844		
INF4			0.677		
ENT1		0.747			
ENT2		0.792			
ENT3		0.731			
ENT4		0.768			
SOC1	0.811				
SOC2	0.834				
SOC3	0.825				
SOC4	0.720				
ATT2					0.803
ATT3					0.774
ATT4					0.774
INT1				0.786	
INT2				0.840	
INT3				0.822	

The results of the structural model assessment are shown in Table 3. The results shows good fit to the study. Specifically, the goodness fit of indices are as follows: CMIN/DF = 1.806; CFI = 0.931; TLI = 0.918; RMSEA = 0.065. The table also shows that all research hypotheses were supported.

TABLE 3. PARAMETER ESTIMATES FOR STRUCTURAL PATHS

Hypotheses	Path	Standardized regression weight	CR	Absolute fit
H ₁	ATT ← INF	0.331	3.901	CMIN/DF = 1.806
H ₂	ATT ← ENT	0.242	2.572	CFI = 0.931
H ₃	ATT ← SOC	0.229	2.447	TLI = 0.918
H ₄	INT ← ATT	0.596	6.380	RMSEA = 0.065

4.4 Discussion

The purpose of this study is to predict the relationship between three main predictors of attitude towards sharing news: (1) the relationship between information and attitude, (2) the relationship between entertainment and attitude, and (3) the relationship between social and attitude. The study also examines the relationship between attitudes and the intention to share the news. All research hypotheses are supported. In other words, this research confirms that information, entertainment, and social as the three main predictors of

attitudes toward news sharing. Furthermore, this study also confirms the relationship between attitudes and the intention to share the news.

The research model was based on inductive and deductive approaches. In other words, all three predictors of attitude towards news sharing were based on finding from inductive approach, and also based on other previous studies (deductive approach). The relationship between attitude and intention was mainly based of attitude theories such as Theory of Planned Behavior and Theory of Trying.

The results of this study indicate the respondent's attitude to sharing knowledge based on the reason for sharing information because the information was felt important, unique, useful, and the latest news for his friends. Sharing the news is also an entertainment. By using social media, respondents can feel happy, relax, can pass the time, and break away from uncomfortable situations. Furthermore, social media also allows for respondents to be closer to friends, more interacting, and feeling connected with friends, and social media is a useful communication channel.

5. Conclusion

This study confirms that information, entertainment, and social are three significant predictors of attitude towards news sharing. Furthermore, this study confirms the relationship between attitude towards news sharing and intention to share news. However, this research cannot be separated from some limitations. The first limitation is related to the use of non-probability sampling design which gives the consequence that the results of this study is to explain the respondents of this study alone but cannot be generalized to different contexts or samples. A second limitation is that this study is a cross-sectional study. In other words, this study only captures the phenomenon at that time only. Notwithstanding the research limitations, this research provides the empirical analysis of the research model that developed through the inductive and deductive approach.

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